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MARKET FOR INFORMATION IN ASYMMETRIC INFORMATION ENVIRONMENTS: INSIDER - OUTSIDER DYNAMICS

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Abstract: *Information asymmetry remains a key driver of inefficiencies in financial markets, where insiders often exploit privileged signals at the expense of outsiders and noise traders. To study this imbalance, we propose a model in which insider information is correlated to varying degrees with the information available to outsiders, allowing us to investigate how correlation alters market quality and profit distribution. The analysis relies not only on theoretical modeling but also on advanced optimization techniques and numerical algorithms designed to compute equilibrium strategies. Through iterative procedures and computational simulations, we determine profit-maximizing equilibria for insiders, outsiders, and noise traders. This approach captures non-linear effects and strategic adjustments that cannot be observed through closed-form analysis alone. Our findings show that higher positive correlation improves liquidity, increases efficiency, and raises the profitability of outsiders and noise traders while reducing insider rents. Negative correlation, in contrast, generates unstable trading dynamics and irregular equilibrium outcomes. These results underscore the importance of algorithmic and numerical optimization methods in capturing the true dynamics of asymmetric markets and provide guidance for future regulatory policies on disclosure and transparency.*

Keywords: *Asymmetric information, insider trading, computational methods, financial market dynamics, correlated signals.*